

LEXICOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF TOPONYMS

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This article is devoted to the lexicographic analysis of the monolingual explanatory dictionary "Collins Concise Dictionary" (2005). In this article, geographical names are taken into consideration and their lexicographic development is analyzed.

Key words: toponym, dictionary, mega structure, macrostructure, choronyms, astionyms, potamonyms, microstructure.

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It is difficult to imagine the modern world without toponyms. Each toponym can carry a wide variety of information: historical, geographical, linguistic, since geographical names are evidence of historical epochs, in which they arose, formed and spread in certain countries [1]. A toponym usually means a proper name (PN), which denotes the name of a geographical object. So, S. I. Ozhegov defines a toponym as the proper name of a separate geographical place (a settlement, a river, land, etc.) [2].

The historical and cultural significance of toponyms cannot be overestimated. Many place names originated before the first written sources, and as a result, they are considered to be part of the pre-written history of the language [3]. For the society, both modern and obsolete toponyms, having a cumulative function, arouse great interest among historians, geographers, linguists, as well as researchers from other fields of knowledge, including lexicographers [3, p. 189].

PN has long attracted the attention of many professional researchers. According to O. A. Leonovich, "It is due to the relatively high degree of preservation of geographical names that scientists have the probability of identifying toponymic models that are characteristic for each locality of the distribution of this language and for each historical epoch" [3, p. 40]. Currently, PN are studied by representatives of a wide range of sciences. In both Russian and English, PN are considered as an integral part of the native speaker's vocabulary and widely used in speech. They perform three distinct linguistic functions: nominative, cognitive and communicative and has a well-defined lexical and cultural background. Therefore, they should also be the subject of careful description in lexicographic sources [1].

In this regard, the analysis of such linguistic units as PN presented in lexicographic sources are of great importance, since, despite certain successes achieved in the field of onomastics, many issues related to the study of the essence of this class of words still remain unsolved [4].

Geographical names are objective witnesses of various historical epochs and their formation. Toponyms can be considered as an object of cultural heritage, since they are associated with historical or cultural events from the life of the people [5]. For this reason, place names are included in such dictionaries of the national language, as Cambridge, Collins, Longman and Oxford. Among others, a large number of geographical names associated with British history are included in "Collins Concise Dictionary" (2005).

An appeal to the study of PN in lexicographic literature is explained by the important role of these lexical units in language communication. Permeating all spheres of human

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activity, they form a numerous and heterogeneous class [8]. They include not only geographic names (place names) and private people's names (anthroponyms), but also names of various objects of culture (chremotonyms), the names of the companies, various societies and associations (ergonyms), the names of specific periods of time (chrononyms), names of celestial bodies (astronyms) and a large number of other diverse titles [8,p 46].

Playing an important role in the language, the PN are characterized by the fact that in greater extent than common nouns, they respond to various social changes, and be a kind of registrars of historical events, happening around them and have their sociological and ideological content, which is largely determined by social, historical, economic and other factors [6].

As you know, the peculiarity of PN is that, in fact, their cultural relatedness is displayed not in the nomination, but in the category of denotation itself. The same object can be named differently by representatives of different cultures, and the name will reflect the peculiarities of the national worldview, word formation, phonetics, and spelling of the nominee's language, but the essence of the named object will not change in any way [1].

Each unique name is inscribed in the culture: it is reflected in the language of the people, in their mythology, proverbs, literature and is connected with the history of this people [7].

Our choice of the Collins Concise Dictionary (2005) is justified by its authority and high citation index. Thus, the subject of this article is the lexicographic analysis of toponyms on the material of the dictionary "Collins Concise Dictionary" [8].

Analysis of the principles of registration of toponyms in the dictionary "Collins Concise Dictionary" has identified the most common models of geographical names. Toponyms are mainly represented by nouns (Bix, Bould), a combination of common nouns in both complex (Hors path) and compound names (Cane End), a combination of the proper name and common noun (Tubney), a combination of an adjective and a common noun (West well, Chill Brook). A few three- and four-syllable phrases consist of a pair of nouns and adjectives (White Horse Hill) or from a prepositional group of words (Isle of Rhea).

The "Collins Concise Dictionary" mega structure is traditional and consists of the "Using this Dictionary" section, a list of Abbreviations, an introductory word, the dictionary itself, and an appendix.

The "Using this Dictionary" section is a short summary, a guide to the microstructure of the dictionary. The authors deliberately deviate from the graphical way of presenting information in the introduction. It should be noted that this guide is quite easy to use and therefore in demand by users.

The macrostructure of this dictionary is organized in alphabetical order from A to Z. Its qualitative composition is quite diverse. The dictionary contains a historical, cultural and linguistic commentary of 123 thousand phrases arranged in alphabetical order, knowledge which is necessary for understanding phenomena and facts. The dictionary offers a wide range of world and regional dialects of English with examples and explanations. Lexicographic analysis of the reference book shows that most of the dictionary is occupied by such types of toponyms as choronyms, which make up 45 % of the dictionary. Among them: London, Florida, Cotton State, Canberra Manchester. This fact is not accidental and is due to the fact that choronyms mean the names of large areas, countries, vast spaces. The dictionary also includes astionyms, the names of the cities: Oakland, Calgary, Norwich,; place names for streets, highways, and driveways – Lombard Street, Regent Street, Abbey Road, Bond Street, Bay Street; potamonyms denoting the names of rivers – The Severn, Tyne, Clyde, Tay, Force [9].

In the microstructure of the dictionary, a detailed definition of the input unit is given:

London ('lʌndən) n 1 the capital of the United Kingdom, a port in S England on the River Thames near its estuary on the North Sea: consists of the City (the financial quarter),

the West End (the entertainment and major shopping centre), the East End (the industrial and former dock area), and extensive suburbs Latin name: Londinium See also City. 2 Greater. the administrative area of London, consisting of the City of London and 32 boroughs (13 Inner London boroughs and 19 Outer London boroughs): formed in 1965 from the City, parts of Surrey, Kent, Essex, and Hertfordshire, and almost all of Middlesex. Pop.: 6 964 400 (1994 est.). Area: 1579 sq. km (610 sq. miles). 3 a city in SE Canada, in SE Ontario on the Thames River: University of Western Ontario (1878). Pop: 303 168 (1991) [9, p. 862].

It should be marked that each input unit is accompanied by a wide set of definitions: grammatical, stylistic, regional, etymological, which are also present in other groups of keywords.

It is necessary to note the presence of etymological issues in the microstructure of the dictionary, which are not available in all dictionaries for general purposes. Etymological issues in "Collins Concise Dictionary", in our opinion, deserve special attention. Unlike most reference books of this type, the etymological characteristics in the dictionary of this publication enclosed in square brackets and placed at the end of the dictionary entry (behind the definition) what meets the user's requirements and significantly increases the informative value of the dictionary:

Jacobean (,dʒækə'biən) adj. 1 History. relating to James I of England or to the period of his rule (1603–25) 2 of or relating to the style of furniture current at this time, characterized by the use of dark brown carved oak. 3 relating to, or having the style of architecture used in England during this period [C18: from New Latin *jacōbaeus*, from *Jacōbus* James] [9, p. 768].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the volume of dictionary entries devoted to the lexicographic analysis of toponyms, which are registered in these applications, significantly exceed the volume of articles of other input units, which fully meets the requirements for lexicographic sources of the new generation. Thus, the authors focus the attention of users on PN data as the main media of cultural information and strive to give them the most complete encyclopedic interpretation.

In general, the "Collins Concise Dictionary" reflects the modern state of the English language and culture. The reference book can also be used as an educational dictionary. The system of issues presented in the dictionary helps to get comprehensive information about the input units.

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